

Influence of Decentralization of Management Reforms on Service Delivery at Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company

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ABSTRACT: Kenya socio-economic development goals are extremely smitten by inadequate supply of water in sensible amount and quality. Delivery of water services is characterized with inefficiency, ineffectiveness, bureaucracy, high costs, weighed down by unnecessary rules, unresponsiveness to public desires, and lack of transparency, despotic and invasive into the personal rights of clients. In urban center County, most water urban service suppliers have faced extreme interference of politics resulting in a negative impact on their revenues and general performance of the organization. The study sought to establish the influence of decentralize management reform on service delivery at Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company. An Ex-post facto research design was adopted for a sample of 223 clients and 113 staff of NAWASCO. Data was collected using semi-structured questionnaires. Data analysis was using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). The paper results yielded a correlation coefficient of $r = (269) = 0.361$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$ and regression coefficient of $\beta = 0.375$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$. This implies that decentralization of management reforms have significant influence on service delivery. The paper recommends that staff members should be adequately trained to build their capacity in the delivery of quality services. Decentralization of services which being the main purpose of devolution, the paper recommends that NAWASCO need to be adequately facilitated to ensure that they deliver quality water services to their clients.

KeyWords: Decentralization, Management Reforms and Service Delivery

I. INTRODUCTION

Decentralization is passing of authority to create selections to the bottom potential level within the structure hierarchy. High level selections are created in an exceedingly delegated powers structure. The highest-hierarchical administrators delegate powers of authority to the lower level, giving themselves an off from drawback finding. In return they specialize in strategy, on top administrators' selections and on supervising works regarding the organization. It conjointly offers extra activities and knowledge to the below the hierarchy administrators and creating selections, so serving to them is promotion (Shilipi, 2009).

In an exceedingly delegated power system; the below the hierarchy administrators will create higher selections than the highest-hierarchy administrators as they are well conversant to the native conditions. A regional manager for instance, who manages promoting and commerce of product is aware of the native behaviors' and wishes of shoppers more than a high-hierarchal administrators who cannot understand the consumers taste and brands. Trade should create quick selections so as to remain competitive. An enterprise doing business should decide to maximize the new innovations in a country that is not its own so as to compete with others. A fast call is needed therefore to act as a shield for corporation to avoid losing their consumers to their competitors. A delegated power atmosphere offers an opportunity to the lower management to research matters creating an acceptable and real time solutions (Shilipi, 2009).

The department dealing with employees has a plus in decentralization management. In an exceedingly delegated structure it is hard for proper evaluation due to negligence by top management. Delegated administrators system offers

chance to lower managers in other levels to show their productivity. They given an opportunity to create selections, so providing them motivation to perform within the organization. The highest-level administrators become privy to truth enablement of the low management which may straightforward give them assignments to perform. However, a person and structure goal in an exceedingly decentralized management is quite difficult. The low management could have different mission totally unique from that of an institution. Other administrators could be too curious to escalate the number of their units so as to maximize profits (Shilipi, 2009).

Water as a basic want and is demanded by a growing population. The United Nations has recommended on the social and economic demands compete for this essential commodity. Women and girls mostly need water for their private sanitation issues. Water is therefore needed also for sanitation issues, to reduce the world burden of disease and improve health, education and productivity of all people. The main challenges are lack of access to safe drinking water, safe sanitations, water scarcity, natural disasters, waste water flowing back into the ecosystem without being re-used, unavailability of management framework, agricultural water usage, industrial water withdrawals for energy (Grojec, 2017).

The World Health Organization has also surveyed on today's water pressure to be on a higher side unlike before. The shifting climate and a growing population has led to water stress and increased risks globally. There has been a progress in tackling this issues but much work needs to be done around the world to make water efficiency a reality. The population around the world draws about four thousand cubic kilometer of water every year. Most of the challenges of insufficient water supply has been caused by poor infrastructure and governance. This worsening scenario of water insufficiency is a problem companies both contribute and experience operational risks. Investors have therefore considered scarcity of water as an indicator of risk and are making investment decisions (Kammeyer, 2017)

There's adequate water within the world for everyone's essential domestic desires. However, poor governance and alternative issues encompassing its distribution, management and therefore the manner it's extracted and harvested from the bottom makes its accessibility problematic. The politics of water distribution that result in inequitable allocation additionally limits people's access. In line with a United States geologic Survey of 2011, there's adequate water within the globe to fulfill the requirements of the earth population. The Report points out that if the worldwide water resources were well used the matter of access to water would be a factor of the past. This position is also held by a United Nation agency that blames the present international water crisis not on a scarcity of installation or technology but rather on the failure within the governance of water. That is, today's water crises don't seem to be caused by the deficiency of water to satisfy people's desires, rather it's a crisis of managing water badly that billions of individuals don't access it. The issues of water within the world are political management, poor governance, discriminatory distribution or outright use of water as a political weapon to reward supporters while denying opponents. Obscurity is that a lot of continents apparently in Africa where management and corruption by authorities, the dearth of acceptable establishments, functionary inertia and a shortage of recent investments in building human capability and physical infrastructure have restricted people's access to water (Okechi,2015).

Decentralization has become a modern answer to several countries' development challenges Unilever worked to include decentralization throughout the company's growth. In each of the divisions around the world it has its own independent unit. Spreading will be outlined as delegation of powers from higher to lower levels in an exceedingly public affairs management and governed system. Decentralization will take two broad models: de-concentration and devolution. First State concentration, conjointly called body spreading, where powers are delegated to the lower managers, or alternatively native persons who are upward responsible to the major administrators for instance districts, provinces, regions or native councils. In distinction, political, or democratic, decentralization conjointly known as devolution means delegation of power downwards to the responsible actors, like appointive native governments (Elliott, 2002).

The paper sought to establish the validity of the following set of research hypotheses;

H₀: There is no significant influence of decentralization management reforms on service delivery at Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company.

H₁: There is a significant influence of decentralization management reforms on service delivery at Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company.

II. METHODOLOGY

The study employed ex-post facto research design targeting the urban water service provider in Nakuru County of 230 employees and 45,000 customers. The choice of the organization's employees was prompted by the fact that these are the persons who execute the daily operations of the organization. The sample comprised of 223 clients and 113 staff of NAWASCO. Data was collected using semi-structured questionnaires. Data analysis was mainly quantitative in which the researcher used descriptions to evaluate the raw information for the purpose of obtaining the percentages of

frequencies, means and standard deviations. Coefficient correlation and regression analysis were used to test the relationship between the study variables.

III. RESULTS

Table 1: Role of decentralization in the Management Reforms

Measurable Indicators	Very large	Large	Moderate	Small	None
Reduction of Non-Revenue water	37 (13.8%)	31 (11.5%)	29 (10.5%)	84 (31.2%)	88 (32.7%)
Customer complains resolved promptly	13 (4.8%)	56 (20.8%)	68 (25.3%)	93 (34.6%)	39 (14.5%)
Bursts and leakages repaired within the Stipulated time	30 (11.2%)	23 (8.6%)	42 (15.6%)	95 (35.3%)	79 (29.4%)
Reduction of illegal connections	51 (19.0%)	68 (25.3%)	33 (12.3%)	41 (15.2%)	76 (28.3%)
Encouraged team work between management and employees	33 (12.3%)	32 (11.9%)	128 (47.6%)	44 (16.4%)	32 (11.8%)

The outcomes on table 4.6 indicated that half of the respondents held the opinion that to a small extent there has been reduction of non-revenue water while majority of the respondents said that to a no extent there has been reduction of non-revenue water. According to the majority of the respondents customer complaints are resolved promptly to a small extent, a third of the respondents held large extent opinion while half of the respondents indicated that to a moderate extent customer complaints are resolved promptly. Further, the results indicate that majority of the participants indicated that finding bursts and leakages are repaired within the stipulated time with meaning that the mandate of pipe repairs is still solely dependent on top management due to logistics leading to delay again. This will affect the consumers services flow as well, the third to the majority held the opinion that to a no extent bursts and leakages are repaired within the stipulated time. The results indicate that second to the largest respondents were of the opinion that to a large extent there has been reduction of illegal connections with the majority of participants indicating to a no extent there has been reduction of illegal connections. The reduction of illegal connections is still slow because employees are not yet passionate about their duties. Further, majority of the participants preferred moderate extent which indicated there is encouragement for team work between management and employees while a third of the respondents to the majority held the opinion that to a large extent there was encouragement for team work between management and employees in NAWASSCO.

Outcomes in Figure 1 states that minority of the respondents specified that to a very large extent management reforms had improved services in the water sector while a third held the opinion that management reforms had improved services in the water sector to a large extent, Majority had the opinion that reforms had improved services by a moderate and again by a small extent respectively.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

		Decentralization Management Reforms	Service Delivery
Decentralization management reforms	Pearson Connection	1	.361**
	P-value		.000
	N	269	269
Service Delivery	Pearson Relationship	.361**	1
	P-value	.000	
	N	269	269

The connection outcome indicates existence of an important not usual relation in the two variables decentralization management reforms and service delivery in Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company $r(269) = 0.361, p = 0.000 < 0.05$.

Further, the results indicate the relation in the two variables, decentralization administration reforms and delivering of services in Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company was of great impact and statistically relevant ($\beta = 0.375, p = 0.000 < 0.05$). It implies when decentralization management reforms are enhanced by an extra unit, service delivery in Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company increases by 0.375. These findings show that decentralization management reforms have played a big role delivering of services in Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company.

These results are true according to (Shilipi, 2009), delegation of power to the lower cadres offers an opportunity on research matters and creating acceptability on real time solutions. It means that employees have not been given mandate

to make amicable solutions concerning issues experienced they are still relying fully on the top management leading to the delay.

It also reflects a true picture according to (Shilipi, 2009) where he has emphasized on decentralization as passing of authority to create selections to the bottom potential level within the structure hierarchy. This means these customers' complaints are not resolved promptly because of bureaucracy in the system. When top management is fully involved in making major decisions in the customer's complaints a lot of delay is experienced leading to inefficiency in the lower levels. Top management should give the area managers at the ground full powers to make wise decisions.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The paper established that the p-values for both correlation and regression analysis were less than 0.005, the null hypothesis 'There is no significant influence of decentralization management reform on service delivery at Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company.' was rejected therefore accepting the alternative hypothesis 'There is a significant influence of decentralization management reform on service delivery at Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company.'. This implies that decentralization management reform had significant influence on service delivery at 5 % levels of significance.

A fair number of the respondents held the opinion that to a small extent there has been a slight change in loss of water. According to the respondent's customer complaints are resolved promptly to a small extent, some of the respondents held large extent opinion while others indicated that to a moderate extent customer complaint are resolved promptly. Further, the results indicate respondents said that to a small extent bursts and leakages are repaired within the stipulated time with few holding the opinion that to a no extent bursts and leakages are repaired within the stipulated time. The results indicate that most respondents held the opinion that to a large extent there has been reduction of illegal connections with a fair number of the respondents indicating a no extent opinion on whether there has been reduction of illegal connections. Further, most respondents indicated that to a moderate extent there is encouragement for working together between the low and high cadres while some held the opinion that to a large extent encouragement for working together as a team in NAWASSCO was good. According to (Elliott, 2002) he has emphasized on decentralization which has become a modern answer to several countries' development challenges. Team work is the key to achieving great returns in the current economy.

It was finalized that decentralization administration reforms has an important impact on delivering of services in Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company. Conclusions can be made that to a small extent there has been reduction of non-revenue water. Customer complaints are resolved promptly to a medium level while to a small number bursts and leakages are repaired within the stipulated time. It can be concluded that to a large extent there has been reduction of illegal connections. Further, to a moderate extent there is encouragement for team work between management and employees in NAWASSCO.

Water services being a devolved function mandated for the county government. In the spirit of devolution, therefore the paper recommends that NAWASSCO need to be adequately facilitated to ensure that they deliver quality water services to their clients.

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